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Research Article

**EXERCISE AND DIETARY HABITS DURING AND BEFORE
PREGNANCY AMONG WOMEN VISITING OPD****Dr. Muhammad Umer Bajwah, Dr. Muhammad Ahmad, Dr. Muhammad Talha Arshad**
Shalamar Medical and Dental College, Lahore**Article Received:** November 2020**Accepted:** December 2020**Published:** January 2021**Abstract:****Objectives:** *To determine the exercise and dietary habits during and before pregnancy among women visiting the gynae OPD at Shalamar hospital Lahore.***Methods:** *It is a cross sectional study. Data was collected from health setups from April to July 2019, by the researchers themselves. The points asked from the mothers and filled by researchers. Sample size was calculated by open epi and it was 200 with 95% of confidence level, 5% of margin of error and 80% power. Analysis of data was done by using statistical program SPSS.***Conclusions:** *Exercise and dietary habits during and before pregnancy is poor among the women visiting the Opd due to lack of knowledge of benefits of exercise and good dietary habits on pregnancy.***Corresponding author:****Muhammad Umer Bajwah,**

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INTRODUCTION:

A women's health and behaviour in pregnancy effect her baby. There is much evidence that regular exercise and balanced diet is important element of treatment and prevention of gestational diabetes, preclampsia and obesity in the mother. Physical activity during pregnancy has been proposed to have numerous health benefits across the life course. Gestational weight gain (GWG) determined by physical activity and dietary intake . High total energy intake as well as higher proportion of protein and lipid of animal origin and lower proportion of carbohydrates associated with GWG.

The American college of obstetrician and gynaecologist proves that maternal lifestyle and nutritional factors before and during pregnancy can influence the pregnancy. The diet should meet the nutritional requirements of macronutrients (carbohydrates, protein, fats) as well as micronutrients (mineral, vitamins). Calories requirement of an adult female of (18-30 years)is approximately 2500kcal per day .The goal of present study is to access the efficiency of the life style Intervention , food intake and physical activity in pregnant women via a randomised controlled trial (RCT) "NOT NEED TO EAT FOR 2" .But not advisable to have a highly

restrictive diet, it is important to eat food of high quality nutrition wise rather than high in kilojoules .Motivational interviewing(MI) is a method that is used in swedish antenatal care to promote motivational and behavior change related to life style factor. The idea is to support patients in their efforts to change an unhealthy lifestyle habits. This method is influenced by Procska & Dielement's theoretical model and developed by Miller & Rollnick.

The metaanalysis concluded that difference in birth weight were minimal to none in women who exercised during pregnancy as compared with women who continued to prefer rest. Exercise does not increase the risk of miscarriages and neonatal complication.

METHODOLOGY:

It is a cross sectional study conducted in Shalamar Hospital, Lahore. Study was completed in duration of 3 months. Sample size was calculated using Open-EPI at 95% confidence level with 5% margin of error and 80% power. The proportion of anticipated factor was taken as 80% and the sample size was calculated to be as 200. Non-probability purposive sampling techniques used. The standard questionnaire was prepared and Filled by conducting interviews of pregnant ladies visiting gynae OPD of Shalamar Hospital Lahore. Analysis of data was done by using statistical program SPSS.

Frequency tables:

Table # 1: Gestational diabetes in previous pregnancies

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	48	24	24	24
No	152	76	76	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table # 2: Exercise before pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	26	13	13	13
No	174	87	87	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table # 3: Walk during pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	68	34	34	34
No	132	66	66	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #4: Walk: before pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	58	29	29	29
No	142	71	71	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #5: Exercise during pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	23	11.5	11.5	11.5
No	177	88.5	88.5	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #6: Climbing stairs before pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	133	66.5	66.5	66.5
No	67	33.5	33.5	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #7: Climbing stairs during pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	133	66.5	66.5	66.5
No	67	33.5	33.5	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #8: Householdwork during pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	156	78	78	78
No	44	22	22	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #9: Householdwork before pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	185	92.5	92.5	92.5
No	15	7.5	7.5	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #10: Effect of exercise on BMI during pregnancy

Do you exercise now?

Count	Yes	No	Total
BMI<25	18	143	161
BMI>25	5	34	39
Total	23	177	200

Table #11: Effect of exercise on BMI before pregnancy

Do you exercise before?

Count	Yes	No	Total
BMI<25	20	141	161
BMI>25	6	33	39
Total	26	174	200

Table #12: Effect of household work on BMI during pregnancy

Householdwork regularly?

Count	Yes	No	Total
BMI<25	128	33	161
BMI>25	28	11	39
Total	156	44	200

Table #13: Special diet during pregnancy

Follow special diet?

Count	Yes	No	Total
BMI<25	21	140	161
BMI>25	6	33	39
Total	27	173	200

Table #14: Melas during pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	3	1.5	1.5	1.5
2	30	15	15	16.5
3	142	71	71	87.5
4	23	11.5	11.5	99
5	2	1	1	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #15: Snacks during pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	78	39	39	39
1	35	17.5	17.5	56.5
2	55	27.5	27.5	84
3	20	10	10	94
4	10	5	5	99
5	2	1	1	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table # 16: Chappatis before pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	7	3.5	3.5	3.5
2	51	25.5	25.5	29
3	116	58	58	87
4	22	11	11	98
5	2	1	1	99
6	2	1	1	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #17: Chappatis during pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	0.5	0.5	0.5
2	32	16	16	16.5
3	114	57	57	73.5
4	28	14	14	87.5
5	10	5	5	92.5
6	11	5.5	5.5	98
7	2	1	1	99
8	1	0.5	0.5	99.5
9	1	0.5	0.5	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #18:milk intake before pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	115	57.5	57.5	57.5
1	71	37.5	37.5	93
2	13	6.5	6.5	99.5
3	1	0.5	0.5	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #19:Milk intake during pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	75	37.5	37.5	37.
1	76	38	38	75.5
2	29	14.5	14.5	90
3	20	10	10	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #20:Dairy products intake before pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	82	41	41	41
1	78	39	39	80
2	35	17.5	17.5	97.5
3	5	2.5	2.5	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #21:Dairy products intake during pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	45	22.5	22.5	22.5
1	85	42.5	42.5	65
2	51	25.5	25.5	90.5
3	15	7.5	7.5	98
4	2	2	1	99
5	1	0.5	0.5	99.5
6	1	0.5	0.5	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #22:Fruits during pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	63	31.5	31.5	31.5
1	90	45	45	76.5
2	39	19.5	19.5	96
3	5	2.5	2.5	98.5
4	3	1.5	1.5	100
Total	200	100	100	

Table #23:Supplements before pregnancy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	178	89	89	89
1	20	10	10	99
2	2	1	1	100
Total	200	100	100	

Result:

This study was performed at gynae OPD Shalamar Hospital Lahore.

Table no 1 shows out of 200 women 152 don't have gestational diabetes during pregnancy.

Table no 2 shows out of 200 women 174 don't exercise before pregnancy.

Table no 3 shows out of 200 women 132 don't walk during pregnancy.

Table no 4 shows out of 200 women 142 don't walk before pregnancy.

Table no 5 shows out of 200 women 177 don't exercise during pregnancy.

Table no 6 shows out of 200 women 133 prefer climbing stairs before pregnancy.

Table no 7 shows out of 200 women 133 prefer climbing stairs during pregnancy.

Table no 8 shows out of 200 women 156 do household work before pregnancy.

Table no 9 shows out of 200 women 185 do household work during pregnancy.

Table no 10 shows out of 161 with normal BMI 18 perform exercise during pregnancy.

Table no 11 shows out of 161 with normal BMI 20 perform exercise before pregnancy.

Table 12 shows out of 161 with normal BMI 128 do household work during pregnancy.

Table no 13 shows out of 161 with normal BMI 21 are following special diet during pregnancy.

Table no 14 shows out of 200 women 142 are taking meats 3 times a day during pregnancy.

Table no 15 shows out of 200 women 55 are taking snacks two times a day during pregnancy.

Table no 16 shows out of 200 women 116 are having 3 chapattis before pregnancy.

Table no 17 shows out of 200 women 114 are having 3 chapattis during pregnancy.

Table no 18 shows out of 200 women 115 are having no milk intake before pregnancy.

Table no 19 shows out of 200 women 76 are having 1 glass of milk during pregnancy.

Table no 20 shows out of 200 women 82 are having no dairy intake before pregnancy.

Table no 21 shows out of 200 women 85 are having 1 dairy product intake during pregnancy.

Table no 22 shows out of 200 women 90 are having one fruit during pregnancy. Table no 23 shows out of 200 women 178 have no supplements before Pregnancy.

DISCUSSION:

The current investigation sought to evaluate the relationship between dietary intake, physical activity, body mass and body weight change before and during pregnancy. The majority of studies identified in our review were observational with few well designed interventional trials. The overall quality of evidence as per our research was moderate for most Outcomes with the exception of BMI (less than and equal to 25) in those (11.5%) who preferred exercise (before pregnancy 13%, during pregnancy 11.5%, table 2&5); climbing stairs (before pregnancy 66.5%, during pregnancy 66.5%, table 6&7), household activities (before pregnancy 92%, during pregnancy 78%, table 8&9), special diet (13.5%, table 13) along

with supplementation than those (BMI > 25) who did not do so.

Pregnancy not surprisingly, was also positively associated with weight gain but the rapid change in BMI was seen in those who had greater total energy intake in the form of cheese, butter, snacks, chapattis (table 14,15, 16, 17, 21) and lesser physical activity (exercise, climbing stairs, and household activities).

Research studies shows that women with gestational diabetes (table 1) are those who have BMI > 25, that can be the result of high energy intake & less physical activity. Engaging in regular physical activity before pregnancy frequently has been associated reduced risk of developing GDM. In a recent clinical trial, a

moderate physical activity program performed thrice weekly during pregnancy was found to improve level of maternal glucose tolerance in healthy, pregnant women. The frequency of those who used to take special diet (13.5%, table 13) and supplementation (table 23) during pregnancy is also not remarkable, the possibility of which can be unawareness, less resources, negligence and also improper health strategies in health system as compared to other developed countries where special attention has been given to maternal-child health.

To summarize health and nutritional status can be improved in women before, during and after pregnancy by emphasizing on proper energy balance components along with proper awareness strategies on mass level.

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